

Device Analyser

Description

The Device Analyser project collects data from Smartphones that use the Android operating system and aggregates data for research and other personal use. Individual phone users are able to participate in the project and receive personalised analytical data about their phone use in return. Over 30,000 users have contributed to the dataset thus far. Device Analyser collects data related to when a phone is turned on or off, when a user makes phone calls or sends texts, the use of apps, WiFi and Bluetooth devices near a phone, and network-based location data. Select data has been supplied to over 200 research groups and over 60 different research groups have signed license agreements for access to the entire dataset.

Benefits

Individual phone users are provided access to analytical data related to their historical Smartphone usage and the Device Analyser program is able to make suggestions about the best data plan and app downloads based on user trends over time. Phone manufacturers are able to access consumer data that has typically been collected for use only by Smartphone service providers, in order to improve their products in response to consumer demand.

The project team also intends to use the data collected from Device Analyser to make recommendations for Smartphone improvement based on actual usage rather than anecdotal reporting or relying manual user input. The data will be analysed to look for patterns and trends in use that may then support additional product development. The data has also been used as part of the permanent 'Information Age' exhibit at the Science Museum in London.

Supporting links

http://www.ubicomp.org/ubicomp2014/calls_competition.php

Accessed 10 June 2016.

http://bit.ly/Device_Analyser_for_Android

Accessed 10 June 2016.

http://bit.ly/Information_age

Accessed 10 June 2016.

http://bit.ly/Device_Analyser

Accessed 20 June 2016.